

Sidelobe Predictions for Spectrally-Disjoint Radar Waveforms

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Abstract—Spectrally-disjoint radar waveforms seek to minimize the amount of energy in a set of frequency bands within the bandwidth of the waveform. Such a waveform will suffer higher range sidelobes than a waveform with a contiguous bandwidth. As we continue to develop these waveforms, it becomes necessary to establish peak sidelobe level ratio (PSLR) and integrated sidelobe level ratio (ISLR) predictions in order to objectively evaluate performance. In this paper, we derive a closed-form prediction for PSLR and ISLR. These predictions provide sidelobe estimates as a function of usable bandwidth. Predictions such as these can aid in the decision making process of an adaptive radar.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the frequency spectrum becomes congested with users and interferers, radar waveform designs seek to make better use of the available discontinuous frequency bands during operation. In particular, HF, VHF, and UHF regions tend to contain many strong emitters and severely limit the available contiguous frequency bands for radar applications, such as foliage penetration (FOPEN). Many [1]–[10] have investigated and proposed tools for confronting this issue. These include the design of waveforms to avoid the interference and the design of receive filters to further reject noise while maintaining a clean system impulse response.

In [7], and extended in [8], small phase perturbations were applied to stepped-frequency and linear-frequency-modulated waveforms to generate frequency nulls at the known locations of interference. Others, most cited within [1], have approached sparse-frequency waveform design with frequency notching and interference suppression techniques. A range sidelobe mask was used in [11] to design SINR optimal waveforms with a specific autocorrelation sequence (ACS). A few [4] have investigated PSD approximation methods for optimal waveform lookup techniques, when waveform optimizations cannot be computed online.

One could consider the closely related, but fundamentally different problem, of designing a transmit waveform that minimizes transmit energy in specific frequency bands, rather than designing a waveform that is avoiding interference, while maintaining desirable envelope and sidelobe characteristics. It is important to distinguish the difference between these problems because their fundamental differences are not immediately obvious, yet the two do have different problem formulations. A waveform designed to avoid interference can

be characterized by metrics like signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) for various assumed interference covariance matrices [12]. A waveform designed to avoid transmitting in specific bands, a spectrally-disjoint waveform, must be characterized using other metrics since interference is not driving the design, and thus, no such SINR can be calculated. Such metrics include average power levels in the undesired frequency bands, peak sidelobe levels, and integrated sidelobe levels.

Metrics such as these can be useful to adaptive radar systems making waveform design decisions in congested frequency spectrums. An adaptive system might sense the spectrum and then make one of the following waveform design decisions: (a) Transmit *between* the sources of interference (choose the largest open band, current technology) (b) Transmit *over* the sources of interference (if they are not authorized users/sources in that band) (c) Transmit a *spectrally-disjoint waveform*, that occupies more than one of the available bands simultaneously (Higher range sidelobes may be detrimental to the radar's performance).

In this paper, we introduce PSLR and ISLR predictions that can aid in this decision making process. These predictions will establish expected sidelobe levels for the waveform ACS, for a set of unusable frequencies without adaptation in the usable frequency bands. We show that our ISLR prediction concurs with the generalized integrated sidelobe level (GISL) bound in [6], and then compare both predictions to the PSLR and ISLR of an alternating projections waveform design [11] and a gradient descent-based waveform and mismatch filter design [1].

The remainder of this paper is outlined as follows. Section II formulates the predictions for PSLR and ISLR. Simulation results are delivered in section III, followed by conclusions and future work in section IV.

II. SPECTRUM MODEL

If we define a transmit waveform as, $s(n) = a(n) \exp \{j\psi(n)\}$, for $n = 0, \dots, N-1$, where $a(n)$ and $\psi(n)$ are the amplitude and phase respectively, of the waveform at time n , then the power spectral density (PSD), $\phi(m)$, of that

waveform can be written as the Fourier transform

$$\phi(m) = \sum_{k=-(N-1)}^{N-1} r(k) \exp \left\{ -j \frac{2\pi mk}{N} \right\} = \mathcal{F} \{r(k)\}, \quad (1)$$

where $r(k)$ is the ACS of the waveform at lag k :

$$r(k) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} s(n)s^*(n-k) = \mathcal{F}^{-1} \{\phi(m)\} \quad (2)$$

To establish analytic PSLR/ISLR predictions for a given disjoint spectrum, we choose a Bernoulli process to model the PSD of a spectrally-disjoint waveform. This means that each frequency of an M -point PSD, $\phi(m)$, is either zero, meaning it is unusable, or one, meaning it is usable.

$$P \{\phi(m)\} = \begin{cases} p, & \phi(m) = 1 \text{ ("usable")} \\ 1-p, & \phi(m) = 0 \text{ ("unusable")} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

for $m = 0, \dots, M-1$ and we choose $M = 2N-1$. This allows us to model the waveform's PSD as a function of usable bandwidth, where each frequency has probability p of being usable. This is equivalent to saying the PSD has a spectral efficiency p , defined in [6] as $p = M_p/M$; the ratio of usable frequencies, M_p , to complete PSD samples, M .

Given a desired PSD, a number of algorithms exist to synthesize a waveform with that PSD [9], [11], [16]. Our focus is to predict performance without realizing or designing waveforms. By defining our PSD model via (3), we can predict a waveform's average performance solely as a parameter of p .

Most radar systems desire waveforms with a thumb-tack ACS. Meaning the largest correlation is at lag $k = 0$, and every other value of the ACS is minimal. All lags from lag zero out to the first minimum of the ACS define the mainlobe, while lags outside the first minimum define the sidelobes. In practice, most systems seek to minimize ISLR and PSLR. A radar system would desire a low integrated sidelobe ratio to prevent masking weak targets. We define ISLR as

$$\text{ISLR} = \frac{\mathbb{E} \left\{ \sum_{\Theta} |r(k)|^2 \right\}}{\mathbb{E} \left\{ \sum_{\Lambda} |r(k)|^2 \right\}} \quad (4)$$

$$\Theta := \{-N+1 \leq k < -\tau\} \cup \{\tau < k \leq N-1\}$$

$$\Lambda := \{-\tau \leq k \leq \tau\}$$

where Θ defines the lags corresponding to the sidelobes of the ACS, Λ defines the lags for the mainlobe, and τ denotes half the width of the mainlobe. A radar system trying to minimize false alarms would desire an ACS with a low peak-to-sidelobe ratio. PSLR is generically defined as

$$\text{PSLR} = \left| \frac{r(0)}{\rho_{SL}} \right|^2 \quad \text{where, } \rho_{SL} = \max_{k \in \Theta} |r(k)|^2. \quad (5)$$

The significance of metrics such as these motivate us to further examine the autocorrelation sequence.

To characterize the ACS, we can examine the first and

second moments of the ACS defined in (2) with a PSD defined by (3). We can compute the mean of the ACS, $\bar{r}(k)$, as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{r}(k) &\triangleq \mathbb{E} \{r(k)\} \\ &= \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \mathbb{E} \{\phi(m)\} \exp \left\{ j \frac{2\pi mk}{M} \right\} \\ &= \begin{cases} p & k = 0 \\ 0 & k \neq 0 \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

and the variance of the ACS, $\sigma_r^2(k)$, as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_r^2(k) &\triangleq \mathbb{E} \left\{ |r(k) - \bar{r}(k)|^2 \right\} \\ &= \mathbb{E} \left\{ \left| \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} (\phi(m) - \mathbb{E} \{\phi(m)\}) \exp \left\{ j \frac{2\pi mk}{M} \right\} \right|^2 \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{M^2} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{l=0}^{M-1} \mathbb{E} \left\{ [\phi(m) - \bar{r}(k)] \right. \\ &\quad \left. [\phi(l) - \bar{r}(k)] \right\} \exp \left\{ j \frac{2\pi k(m-l)}{M} \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{M^2} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \sum_{l=0}^{M-1} p(1-p) \delta_{m=l} \\ &= \frac{1}{M^2} \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} p(1-p) \\ &= \frac{p(1-p)}{M}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

To validate the variance prediction, we generated a Bernoulli sequence of length M , for varying values of p . For each value of p we generated 500 Bernoulli sequences, recording the variance of each and averaging, to get an average variance for each value of p . Figure 1 shows the average variances in black and our predicted variance in purple.

Fig. 1: Eqn. (7) variance prediction for $M = 511$. The black curve represents the averaged variance for each spectral efficiency for 500 Monte Carlo trials of generating a PSD from a Bernoulli distribution.

We can predict the ISLR for a waveform with a PSD as in (3), by utilizing the first and second moments. Breaking down our definition of ISLR shows that integrating the sidelobe variance and normalizing by the ACS peak squared is approximately equivalent to ISLR:

$$\text{ISLR}(p) \approx \frac{(M-1)\sigma_r(k)^2}{r(0)^2} = \frac{M-1}{M} \frac{1-p}{p} \quad (8)$$

This is within a factor of $(M-1)/M$ of the generalized integrated sidelobe level bound derived in [6] for the high average pass-to-stopband power ratio (APSPR) case. To verify this we ran the same Bernoulli experiment described for Figure 1, but recording the ISLR of the ACS rather than the variance. Figure 2 shows that the average ISLR of a spectrally-disjoint waveform with a PSD like (3), which follows our predicted ISLR(8).

Fig. 2: ISLR predictions for $M = 511$. The green curve is the GISL bound [6] where $\text{APSPR} = 1000$. The black curve represents the averaged ISLR for each spectral efficiency for 500 Monte Carlo trials of generating a PSD from a Bernoulli distribution.

When M is large, the distribution of the sidelobes of the ACS are well represented by $N(\bar{r}(k), \sigma_r^2(k))$ according to the Central Limit Theorem [13], as shown in Figure 3 and 4. These figures were generated by fixing p , generating 500 Bernoulli sequences, and storing the ACS of each Bernoulli sequence. The mainlobe region was removed from each ACS. Then, the sidelobes were concatenated to form one large vector of sidelobes for a particular value of p . Histograms were computed using the real and imaginary parts of the sidelobes, and are shown in blue. A Gaussian PDF was estimated and fitted using the sidelobes, and plotted in red.

Fig. 3: Real part of ACS sidelobes for 500 Monte Carlo trials compared to a Gaussian PDF when $p = 0.6$ and $M = 511$.

Fig. 4: Imaginary part of ACS sidelobes for 500 Monte Carlo trials compared to a Gaussian PDF when $p = 0.6$ and $M = 511$.

Therefore, the squared magnitude of the sidelobes will be well represented by an exponential distribution,

$$f_e(x; \lambda) = \begin{cases} \lambda \exp\{-\lambda x\}, & x \geq 0 \\ 0, & x < 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

with $\lambda = 1/2\sigma^2(k)$ [13]. This is verified by computing the histogram of the squared magnitude of the sidelobes from Figs. 3 and 4, and is shown in blue in Figure 5. An exponential PDF is also fitted and shown in red.

Fig. 5: Magnitude squared of ACS sidelobes for 500 Monte Carlo trials compared to a exponential PDF when $p = 0.6$ and $M = 511$.

The maximum of a sequence of standard ($\lambda = 1$) exponentially distributed random variables is asymptotically ($N \rightarrow \infty$) represented with the Gumbel distribution (Fisher-Tippett Type I) [14], [15],

$$f_g(x; \mu, \beta) = \frac{1}{\beta} \exp \left\{ -\frac{x - \mu}{\beta} - \exp \left\{ -\frac{x - \mu}{\beta} \right\} \right\} \quad (10)$$

with location parameter $\mu = 0$ and scale parameter $\beta = 1$. For finite M , we observed that $\mu = 1/M$ and $\beta = 1/\lambda = 2\sigma_r^2(k)$ ¹. Therefore, if we rewrite PSLR as,

$$\text{PSLR} = \left| \frac{r(0)}{\rho_{SL}} \right|^2 = E \{ \max \{ |r(k)| \} \}, \quad \forall k \neq 0 \quad (11)$$

we can predict the PSLR by using the expected value of a random variable $X \sim f_g(x; \mu, \beta)$ and normalizing by the ACS peak squared,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{PSLR} &= E \{ X \} \frac{1}{p^2} \\ &= [\mu + \gamma\beta] \frac{1}{p^2} \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{M} + \gamma 2\sigma_r^2(k) \right] \frac{1}{p^2} \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{M} + 2\gamma \frac{p(1-p)}{M} \right] \frac{1}{p^2} \\ &= \frac{1}{Mp^2} + 2\gamma \frac{1-p}{Mp} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where $\gamma = .5772$ (Euler's Constant) [15].

To verify this we ran the same Bernoulli experiment described for Figure 1, but recording the PSLR of the ACS rather than the variance. Figure 6 shows the PSLR prediction, and the average PSLR of a Bernoulli sequence modeled PSD for

¹We arrived at this μ and β by examining the asymptotic relationship between the standard exponential distribution and the standard Gumbel distribution in [14] and verifying each empirically.

500 Monte Carlo trials. Figure 6 shows the PSLR prediction to work well for all values of p .

Fig. 6: Eqn. 12, PSL predictions for $M = 511$. The black curve represents the averaged PSL for each spectral efficiency for 500 Monte Carlo trials of generating a PSD from a Bernoulli distribution.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

An infinite number of PSDs can be represented by a specific spectral efficiency. A spectral efficiency of 0.7 represents a waveform whose spectrum has two large bands of energy comprising 70% of the waveform's bandwidth. A spectral efficiency of 0.7 also represents a waveform who occupies many single frequencies comprising 70% of the waveform's bandwidth. The sidelobes for these waveforms are likely to be very different. For this reason, we must use a Monte Carlo simulation to compare our predictions to the average PSLR and average ISLR of spectrally-disjoint waveforms.

We compare our predictions to the average PSLR and ISLR of an alternating projections (AP) algorithm [11] and a mismatched waveform/filter design based on a variation of [1] for a range of spectral efficiencies. This is done by varying the spectral efficiency, p , and generating 1000 Bernoulli sequences, each of length 511, for each p . The Bernoulli sequence is treated as the desired PSD for each waveform design. The PSLR and ISLR of each design is recorded and averaged. The average PSLR and ISLR for each design is compared to our PSLR and ISLR predictions for each value of p .

A. Algorithm 1

The alternating projections approach used here is equivalent to that of [9] and [16], and precisely obtained from [11]. Given desired time domain amplitudes, z , and a desired Fourier transform magnitude (FTM), q , find s with $|s| = z$ that minimizes the cost function J :

$$J(s) = ||\mathbf{F}s - \mathbf{q}\|^2, \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{F} is the discrete Fourier Transform matrix. For our problem, the desired time-domain envelope, \mathbf{z} , would be all ones, while the desired FTM, \mathbf{q} , would be equal to an instantiation of Bernoulli trials for a specific p . This discrete-time spectrum shaping problem becomes that of solving the optimization problem

$$\inf_{\mathbf{s} \in U} J(\mathbf{s})$$

where the time domain constraint set is defined as

$$U := \{\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{C}^N : |\mathbf{s}| = \mathbf{z}\}.$$

Each entry of the vector \mathbf{s} is defined by $s(n) = z(n) \exp\{j\psi(n)\}$ where $\psi(n) \in \mathbb{R}$ for all n . Thus, the constrained optimization problem in (13) can be converted into an unconstrained problem by minimizing $J(\mathbf{s})$ with respect to $\boldsymbol{\psi} = [\psi(1) \dots \psi(N)]^T$ instead of \mathbf{s} . Our final complex waveform, \mathbf{s} , is close to achieving our desired FTM, but is constant modulus.

B. Algorithm 2

In [1], the author derives a spectrally-disjoint transmit waveform and receive filter for UWB synthetic aperture radar for FOPEN. A phase-only transmit waveform design is used to ensure constant amplitude. The transmit waveform is defined as, $s(n) = \exp\{j\phi(n)\}$, for $n = 1, \dots, N$ with transmit penalty function

$$J_T = \mathbf{s}^H \mathbf{R} \mathbf{s}.$$

where we modify \mathbf{R} to be the covariance matrix of an instantiation of Bernoulli trials for a specific p . The phase is computed using gradient descent

$$\phi^{(p+1)}(n) = \phi^{(p)}(n) - \mu \frac{\partial J_T}{\partial \phi^{(p)}(n)}$$

$$\frac{\partial J_T}{\partial \phi^{(p)}(n)} = 2\text{Im} \left\{ \exp\{-i\phi(n)\} \sum_m R(m, n) \exp\{i\phi(m)\} \right\}$$

The receive filter, \mathbf{h} , designed in [1], uses a convex weight to minimize range sidelobes and receiving energy from the specified frequency bands. The filter is computed analytically using

$$\mathbf{h} = \boldsymbol{\Phi}^{-1} \mathbf{s} (\mathbf{s}^H \boldsymbol{\Phi}^{-1} \mathbf{s})^{-1},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\Phi} &= \beta \boldsymbol{\Gamma} + (1 - \beta) \mathbf{R} + \lambda \mathbf{I}, \\ \boldsymbol{\Gamma} &= \mathbf{S}^H \mathbf{S}. \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} s(1) & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ s(2) & s(1) & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ s(N) & s(N-1) & \dots & s(1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & s(N) \end{bmatrix}.$$

For stable inverse computations, the diagonal loading term, λ is set to 10^{-5} .

C. Simulation Results

Figure 7 shows the average ISLR of Algorithm 1 in blue, the average ISLR of Algorithm 2 in green, and the ISLR prediction in purple.

Fig. 7: ISLR predictions for $M = 511$ and the average ISLR of each waveform design.

As the spectral efficiency approaches either extreme, zero or one, the variance of the sidelobes is decreasing. As the variance of the sidelobes decreases, the sidelobes are not as well represented by a Normal distribution. We believe this is why we achieve the best ISLR predictions at $p = 0.5$. It is not completely understood why the average ISLR of Algorithm 2 is not monotonic. This behavior could be the result of the use of a mismatched filter, while our model assumes a matched filter.

Figure 8 shows the average PSLR of Algorithm 1 in blue, the average PSLR of Algorithm 2 in green, and the PSLR prediction in purple.

Fig. 8: PSLR predictions for $M = 511$ and the average PSLR of each waveform design.

Again, we see the best PSLR predictions for spectral efficiencies near $p = 0.5$, and it is not completely understood why the average PSLR of Algorithm 2 is not monotonic. We would expect the peak sidelobes for a constant unity PSD to be near $10\log_{10}(511)$ or -27 dB. As expected, each curve in Figure 8 trends to -27 dB PSLR at $p = 1$ for $M = 511$.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have derived the autocorrelation sequence mean and variance of a spectrally-disjoint waveform by modeling the waveform's power spectral density as a sequence of Bernoulli random variables. This allowed us to develop closed-form predictions for average ISLR and average PSLR, for any percentage of usable bandwidth. We have demonstrated that our analysis is a good predictor for average performance of spectrally-disjoint waveforms. Future work includes a more practical model for the power spectral density of a spectrally-disjoint waveform, one where the frequencies being usable or unusable are correlated, rather than being independent from one another. Future work should also include bounds on the radar performance rather than predictions.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Lindenfeld, "Sparse frequency transmit-and-receive waveform design," *IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 851–861, 2004.
- [2] G. Wang and Y. Lu, "Sparse frequency transmit waveform design with soft power constraint by using PSO algorithm," in *IEEE Radar Conference, 2008. RADAR'08*, 2008, pp. 1–4.
- [3] —, "Designing sparse frequency waveform using iterative algorithm," in *Radar Symposium (IRS), 2010 11th International*, 2010, pp. 1–4.
- [4] C. W. Rossler and L. K. Patton, "Rapid waveform adaptation for nearly optimal detection in colored interference," in *Cognitive Information Processing (CIP), 2010 2nd International Workshop on*, 2010, pp. 232–236.
- [5] H. He, P. Stoica, and J. Li, "Waveform design with stopband and correlation constraints for cognitive radar," in *Cognitive Information Processing (CIP), 2010 2nd International Workshop*, 2010, pp. 344–349.
- [6] G. Wang and Y. Lu, "Designing single/multiple sparse frequency waveforms with sidelobe constraint," *Radar, Sonar Navigation, IET*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 32–38, 2011.
- [7] K. Gerlach, "Thinned spectrum ultrawideband waveforms using stepped-frequency polyphase codes," *Aerospace and Electronic Systems, IEEE Transactions on*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 1356–1361, Oct. 1998.
- [8] M. Cook, T. Higgins, and A. Shackelford, "Thinned spectrum radar waveforms," in *Waveform Diversity and Design Conference (WDD), 2010 International*, 2010, pp. 238–243.
- [9] R. Kassab, M. Lesturgie, and J. Fiorina, "Alternate projections technique for radar waveform design," in *Radar Conference - Surveillance for a Safer World, 2009. RADAR. International*, 2009, pp. 1–4.
- [10] T. Miller, L. Potter, and J. McCorkle, "RFI suppression for ultra wide-band radar," *IEEE transactions on aerospace and electronic systems*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 1142–1156, 1997.
- [11] L. Patton, "On the Satisfaction of Modulus and Ambiguity Function Constraints in Radar Waveform Optimization for Detection," Ph.D. dissertation, Wright State University, 2009.
- [12] S. Frost and B. Rigling, "Performance comparison for constrained radar waveform design," in *Radar Conference (RADAR), 2011 IEEE*, may 2011, pp. 724–728.
- [13] H. Stark and J. Woods, *Probability and random processes with applications to signal processing*. Prentice Hall Upper Saddle River, NJ, 2002.
- [14] S. Kotz and S. Nadarajah, *Extreme value distributions: theory and applications*. World Scientific Publishing Company, 2000.
- [15] R. Fisher and L. Tippett, "Limiting forms of the frequency distribution of the largest or smallest member of a sample," in *Mathematical Proceedings of the Cambridge Philosophical Society*, vol. 24, no. 02. Cambridge Univ Press, 1928, pp. 180–190.
- [16] S. Pillai, K. Y. Li, and H. Beyer, "Reconstruction of constant envelope signals with given fourier transform magnitude," in *Radar Conference, 2009 IEEE*, may 2009, pp. 1–4.